

The Development of Social-Emotional Psychology of Students from Broken Home Families at Senior High Schools in Palu City, Indonesia

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to identify and analyze the psychology of social-emotional development of learning Islamic religious education of broken home families to students, then examine the process of approaching Islamic religious education learning of broken home families to students, as well as analysis of learning outcomes of Islamic religious education of the broken home families to students at senior high schools in Palu. This study used a descriptive qualitative approach; the data collection techniques were observation, interviews, and documentation. Then, it is technically analyzed using data reduction, data presentation, and data verification, and ends with conclusions showing that the psychology of socio-emotional development in broken-home families at senior high schools in Palu shows that the role of Islamic religious teachers can all be handled properly so that students are polite with teachers, responsible for doing assignments, motivated, and obedient to school rules. The learning approach applied to broken home families for senior high schools starts from determining the material to determining learning media sources following the content of the 2013 Curriculum with five forms of approach, namely habituation, psychophysics, rational, dynamic, functional, and exemplary. Then, in analyzing the learning outcomes of students from broken-home families at senior high schools in Palu, there is a difference, but not too much. This is due to social-environmental differences that can psychologically affect learning achievement.

KEYWORDS: Broken Home Family, Developmental Psychology, Students, Social Emotional.

INTRODUCTION

Home is the womb of the family, where children face future growth and development under the supervision of both parents (Engle, Castle, & Menon, 1996). Thus, the vital role of parents is to maintain family harmony so that the child's psychological stability is maintained. However, on the other hand, if the parents are no longer harmonious or even divorced, the child will become unstable in behavior, life, and psychology. Because, after all, children are copies of their parents. Therefore, due to the behavior of parents who often argue or even divorce, it is natural that children are angry, lack self-confidence, feel inferior, and even have low self-esteem towards the environment both in the household and social environment in carrying out life in this world.

In the household, it is not uncommon for rifts to occur in relationships, which eventually lead to divorce, so marriage is symbolized as an inner and outer bond between a man and a woman as husband and wife to form a family with the birth of children as a result of marriage based on belief in the Supreme God is no longer fit for purpose (BODENMANN, LEDERMANN, & BRADBURY, 2007). In addition, the family is the first place of socialization for children, which underlies the levels of psychological, mental, and educational formation. In this case, the child does not only need education, but he always longs for guidance, direction, care, protection, responsibility, and a good role model from his parents, the school environment, and the community environment where the child grows and develops.

The problem of broken home families that lead to divorce nowadays is a common phenomenon in society (Brandwein, Brown, & Fox, 1974). A lack of understanding and poor communication or openness between partners cause the current divorce phenomenon (Apostolou, Constantinou, & Anagnostopoulos, 2019). Some literature states that several factors influence the divorce of parents to children, including the age and personality of the child when the parents separate. In addition, the impact of divorce on children is also seen in the forms of behavior, feelings, thoughts, and habits, which can be seen in increased sadness, anxiety, confusion, fear, guilt, and habits that are dominated by negative things.

This phenomenon is illustrated in preliminary observations at the religious court, which showed that the rate of broken home (divorce) cases in Palu is relatively high. Thus, there may be many children or students at the elementary, junior high, senior high,

and Islamic Senior High School levels in Palu. Then, the results of initial observations conducted at Senior High Schools found twenty-two who fell into the category of broken home families. From several students who experienced cases of broken home families, researchers were interested in researching the psychology of socio-emotional development of Islamic religious education learning for broken home families students, then how to analyze the process of approaching Islamic religious education learning approaches for broken home families to students and how analysis of Islamic Religious Education learning outcomes for Broken Home families in Students at Senior High Schools in Palu?

METHODOLOGY

This study uses qualitative methods. In qualitative research, the use of theory is only a guide so that the research focus is in accordance with the facts in the field (Nurdin & Pettalongi, 2022; Nurdin, Stockdale, & Scheepers, 2016). The data was collected through direct observation, in-depth interviews, and written document analysis at the research site (Rusli, Hasyim, & Nurdin, 2021; Rusli & Nurdin, 2022). In other words, the psychology of social-emotional development of learning Islamic religious education of the broken home families to students at a junior high school in Palu City, Indonesia, during direct observation and in-depth interviews with them. The data analysis technique in this research uses a deductive thinking technique, which can be interpreted as a research procedure that produces deductive data from the sample that has been explained by the author, namely teachers in the field of Islamic education from class teachers, students, principals and other teachers who are related to the problems. Data analysis was conducted using thematic analysis from Corbin and Strauss (2003). The analysis started with open, axial, and selective coding. The final result of the data analysis is themes found from the data. The location of this research is in Palu City, located in Central Sulawesi, Indonesia.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Every husband and wife often have conflicts that lead to divorce. Children often become victims, especially psychologically, affecting future psychological development (Handayani & Nurdin, 2021). During the process of conflict in the family, the psychological development of children will be affected. For example, when you see your parents fighting. Even the struggle for child custody is one of the triggers that makes his spiritual development not optimal. When this continues, the children will harbor a wound in their hearts. Not infrequently among the victims of parental divorce, some children find it difficult to learn. In this condition, children need help so they don't dissolve in sadness.

Following the results of research at Senior High Schools, it can be seen that the subjects react differently to broken home families. Some of them deny denial because students can accept the facts (Askar, Adawiyah, & Nurdin, 2021). However, some try to deny all the emotions that arise, including when they experience the loss of a parent. In addition, anger will appear within him, which cannot be expressed in words, only through teachers and friends.

These stages make it difficult for them to accept all the facts and realize that their parents are not getting along well. However, some students can react calmly and reverse this fact so that they become more motivated so that this does not happen to them in the future. Meanwhile, during the depression stage, the participants experienced a real sense of loss, which could slowly develop into depression. This is because a feeling of loneliness, loss, and sadness begins to be felt in that phase. However, in the end, the child will open up to the reality. The closest people to students are teachers, family, and friends who need to accompany them because their presence and affection can help restore habits previously done to help them face the fact that both parents are still there no matter what.

Following the findings in the field at senior high schools in Palu, it can be seen that the social-psychological development of students who come from broken home families shows differences or similarities in terms of behavior, but if it is related to the theory which states that children whose families not harmonious rather difficult to adapt to the environment can be refuted by itself due to the fact states that students in broken home families can behave well, as shown in the table below.

Table 1. Description of Subject and Activities

Aspects of Social Psychology	Subject 1 AS	Subject 2 MT	Subject 3 HS	Subject 4 SS	Subject 5 AR	Subject 5 IR
cognitive	Quiet, but solved the problem	Complete the assignments given by the teacher	More active and self-adjustment is controlled	Complete all assignments from the teacher	Best in completing the task	Active in expressing opinions
Emotional ability	express and understand the feelings of others, but sensitive	Cheerful, active in school extracurricular activities	Empathize with friends but be emotional.	Independent, strong ability, polite to adapt, diligent worship	Supportive, polite, respectful attitude to anyone, diligent in prayer, easy to get upset	Diligent, polite, respectful attitude to anyone, diligent prayer
Social	Diligent appear during the discussion.	Loving and likes to help friends	Likes to help friends according to tribes	Likes to help, good social relations among friends and teachers	Good social relations among friends and teachers	The social spirit helps, and social relations among friends and teachers are good.

Data source: 2022 Research Findings

The results of the field findings, as illustrated in the table, show that the psychological development of students from broken-home families tends to be better in cognitive, emotional, and social aspects, meaning that they can adapt and be more active and obedient.

Then, based on the findings of the approach process used by Islamic religious education teachers to broken-home students at senior high schools in Palu, there are differences and similarities in the form of approach in the teaching and learning process of Islamic religious education for students who experience broken home from their families. The differences and similarities can be seen as attached in the table below.

Table 2. Approach and Results

Approach	Method	Learning process	Results
Approach habituation	The exemplary method	The teacher or educator will divide into groups by displaying different characters and then analyzing the characters that can be emulated.	Learners are able to complete themselves from the experience of people being emulated so that it can be applied both at school and outside of school.
Psychophysics	Plus lecture method	The teacher detects each case faced by students; these cases are usually with various motives, so a variety of solving techniques is needed for each case.	Students can overcome and be strong in dealing with psychological forms.
Rational emotive	QnA and Giving assignments	The teacher gives assignments in narrative form, then prepares	The formation of attitudes, perceptions, how to think about the beliefs and views of irrational students become rational

		questions and answers for all assignments	
functional	Role Method	The teacher gives roles or functions that students cannot take so that the students will automatically form a sense of responsibility.	The formation of social responsibility and the soul of students
Keteladanan	Mmetode pemberian contoh.	Guru yang senantiasa bersikap baik kepada setiap orang yakni: secara langsung memberikan keteladanan bagi peserta didiknya	Terbentuknua sikap tolada, patu, taat pada semua orang, sengan membatu teman tanpa melihat suku
Story	Assignments	Giving assignments to students individually according to experiences or stories of difficult people's journeys to being successful, and then making them in the form of writing and stories.	Increase the enthusiasm for learning and the attitude of independence and self-confidence for students, especially those who come from broken home families.
Giving Motivation	Giving Rewards	Teachers in each learning process will be given reinforcement in terms of self-development, discipline, studying, and worship	Increase Learning Motivation
kinship	Discussion	The teacher provides opportunities for students to describe the content of the lesson and form groups.	Increased sense of kinship and active in issuing opinions
Ice breaking approach	<i>ice breaking</i>	The teacher requires that each student make a group, and each group must have a jargon. When their group wants to appear, they must display jargon related to the material.	Eliminate boredom, anxiety, and fatigue in class
Humanistic	Discussion and Field trip	The teacher forms groups and makes social activities among friends and good teachers.	Creating a sense of comfort, joy, enthusiasm, and initiative in the learning process is good and forms a social spirit of helping and good social relations among friends and teachers.

Analysis of Islamic religious education learning outcomes for broken home families in students at senior high schools in Palu shows that learning outcomes are the students' level of success in learning subject matter at school, which is expressed in scores obtained from test results based on a number of subject matter. Student learning outcomes are abilities that children acquire after going through learning activities. So that with the learning outcomes obtained, students will know their capabilities. Children who are successful in learning are those who succeed in achieving learning goals. The meaning of learning outcomes, namely the changes that occur in students, both concerning cognitive, affective, and psychomotor aspects as a result of learning activities. Learning outcomes are the final part of the learning process; in other words, the purpose of learning is to get good results. Many students experience problems in learning, as a result of which the learning outcomes they achieve could be higher. Students are required to master several subject matter that the school has determined. If students cannot achieve good learning outcomes, it will be a problem for them. It is increasingly clear that student learning outcomes result from a process in which several factors influence each other. Based on research conducted by the author at senior high schools in Palu, in terms of the learning outcomes of students from broken-home families, the authors collect data or obtain information from teachers and students from broken-home families. Data were obtained through interviews and observations during the learning process or students' breaks, then added to acquiring information

from the principal or counseling teacher. As for the description of student learning outcomes, it can be seen in the description of the findings of the psychological and emotional development of students in broken-home families at senior high schools in Palu as follows: To support this research, the researcher presents the results of research related to low learning outcomes on students. That is, there are positive and negative impacts on the learning of students who experience broken homes with the learning outcomes of students at senior high schools in Palu, each with the initials SS, AR, IR, as evidenced by obtaining a Religious education value above the Minimum Completeness Criteria of 70, as seen in the following table 3:

Table 3. The subject of Studies and Results

Subjects.	Subject 1 SS	Subject 2 AR	Subject 3 IR
Fiqhi	80	81	79
Aqida Akhlak	89	85	89
SKI	86	89	90
Al Qur'an Hadis	80	89	90

Changes in behavior mark standards in measuring learning outcomes, changes in behavior from learning outcomes are relatively permanent, changes in behavior do not have to be observed during the learning process but can be potential, changes in behavior are the result of practice or experience, experience or practice can provide reinforcement. The principles of learning concerning human potential and behavior learning require a process and phasing as well as the self-maturity of students. Knowledge will be more mature, stable, and effective if driven by motivation from within the school and outside the school environment (Askar, Pettalongi, & Nurdin, 2022).

Then, the description of the learning outcomes of broken home students at senior high schools in Palu, talking about student learning outcomes, is determined by the figure of a teacher. Teachers have a significant role in formatting their students at school in shaping personality, which is expected to be a milestone in the success of education and cannot be separated from the role of the teacher. According to the principal, the relationship between teachers and students must be harmonious so that the noble goals of education can be achieved without obstacles (Askar et al., 2021). In connection with its function as an educator and mentor, it is necessary to share the role of the teacher. The role of this teacher will always describe behavior patterns according to the psychological development of students as expected in various interactions with students, fellow teachers, and other staff. As stated in Law No. 14 of 2005 concerning Teachers and Lecturers article 10, paragraph 1, that teacher competence includes pedagogical competence, personal competence, professional competence, and social competence obtained through professional education.

Pedagogic competence is managing student learning, understanding, design, and implementation of knowledge, learning evaluation, and student development to actualize their various potentials (Jimoyiannis, 2010). Professional competence is the ability to master learning material in a broad and in-depth manner, which allows guiding students to meet the competency standards set out in national education standards. Personal competence is a personality ability that is stable, wise, mature, authoritative, able to make himself a good role model for his students, and has a noble character (Leiba-O'sullivan, 1999; Riggio, 1999). Social competence is the ability of educators as part of the community to communicate and socialize well with all school members and the community around where they live and to be able to maintain the good name of their profession inside and outside of school.

The description above shows that professional teachers have competencies that are not only about academic abilities but other competencies that must also be owned by an experienced teacher, such as social competence, which makes the teacher an individual who cannot stand alone, requires the help of others and becomes a teacher. Teachers always socialize with individuals who are around their environment. Personal competence allows the teacher to organize his own attitude and character well so that he can become a figure worthy of being emulated by students, both within and outside the school environment. Of course, teacher professionalism will have implications for student learning outcomes in the form of students' cognitive, affective, and psychomotor development.

Based on the explanation above, it can be concluded that the teacher's task in teaching or education is not only limited to learning activities, but more than that, he must also be able to solve various problems faced by students, including family problems in students because this can disrupt psychology and student learning concentration. Because of that, teachers at senior high schools in Palu have a strategic role in education, mainly Islamic Religious education as a subject area that deals a lot with the religious development of students. Other adequate educational resources are often meaningless if good-quality teachers do not accompany them. It is sufficient that the effect will affect students' learning outcomes. Still, with the results achieved, evaluating the abilities of students who experience a broken home at school is possible. Based on the results of interviews and findings of researchers with Islamic religion teachers, the learning achievement of broken home students can be seen from the results of the test scores of students who became informants in this study, which can be seen in the following table 4:

Table 4. Students and Learning Outcomes

No.	Subject Initials	Learning Outcomes of Islamic Religious Education
1	AS	83
2	MT	85
3	HS	91

Based on the table above, it can be explained that the learning outcomes of broken home students in Islamic religious education subjects at senior high schools in Palu by applying critical thinking skills-based learning can improve students' learning abilities and learning activeness. As revealed by Mr. Shodikin, a teacher of Islamic religious education, the learning outcomes of students using critical thinking skills-based learning improved better than before, which can be seen from the average score obtained by students. Before using critical thinking skills-based learning, the average value obtained only ranged from numbers to numbers. This can be explained according to the table and the results of the interviews above. The learning outcomes of students with the application of critical thinking skills-based learning improve better with the acquisition of an average score of 87, 90. While the learning outcomes obtained by students before using learning based on critical thinking skills only get an average score between 70.00 and 80.00.

The learning outcomes of students by applying Islamic religious education learning based on critical thinking skills not only provide satisfactory grades but are also able to increase the activity of students in terms of thinking even more actively in expressing their opinions. As revealed by MT (Initials), learning Islamic religious education that uses critical thinking skills is very good because all students can participate in learning. Then, students can express opinions or ideas when discussing a given problem to find a solution or way out. Based on the interview above, it can be understood that learning Islamic religious education based on critical thinking skills is student-centered learning because students are actively involved in the learning process and can improve their learning abilities by providing arguments and expressing opinions in solving problems. AS (Initials) expressed that in learning Islamic religious education by applying critical thinking skills-based learning, my friends and I will be motivated to be active in learning. Then, with learning like this, my friends and I will also be more active because when discussing with friends, we can exchange information to broaden our horizons and train ourselves to express our opinions.

The statement of a student can be explained that learning Islamic religious education based on critical thinking skills where students will be more active and able to solve problems by exchanging information by themselves can add insight into knowledge, especially in terms of expressing opinions about the issues discussed in the end able to improve students' thinking skills. The description above shows that teachers are parents who naturally correct children's behavior so that they can continue living their lives and realize their aspirations by displaying good learning outcomes as they should. The attention given by a teacher to students, especially students with a bad background coming from broken homes, is beneficial in straightening out the goals of this nation's education, namely to make young people smart and have noble character. Habituation in this school is also one of the outstanding policies where a good role as a professional educator is to facilitate and be able to solve problems that exist in the world of education. The deviant behavior patterns of children can be adequately resolved with the cooperation of teachers, families, and students in maintaining student achievement. In this way, please continue to support one another to create excellent and noble personalities so that they continue to work and excel to reap the success or success of all to prosper in this dignified life.

There are many challenges for teachers in trying to strengthen students, especially those from broken-home families today, who often behave negatively, which violates the norms that apply in society. One of the triggers for deviations these students commit is the family factor or broken home because they are psychologically somewhat disturbed. Parents, both father and mother, have their respective functions in supporting the development of students. The existence of harmony between father and mother in carrying out their roles will help children achieve good results so that they are ready for all problems that exist in their life.

In theory, broken home families can negatively affect students if they are not addressed immediately (Rodgers, 1996). Broken homes can result from many factors, including divorced parents, lack of communication and openness in the family, and lack of attention from parents to children, which can trigger an atmosphere of disharmony and discomfort for students in learning. In such circumstances, children or students often feel uncomfortable in the family. Children often run away from home and fight with their parents, and it is not uncommon for them to vent their frustration on negative things. In addition to the above, the main factor that significantly influences broken-home family students' mentality is the ability to self-adjust.

Students from broken home families at senior high schools in Palu can adjust their self-adjustment as evidenced by their achievements and ability to adapt to friends who can go well. This proves that it is a must for every student or child to adapt to their environment if they help children lead a good life, of course. Self-awareness of a learner also has a vital role in supporting a good personality because awareness of a reasonable person grows from within a person (Howard, 2011). Self-awareness is the main pillar that gives strength and good personal formation. With a unique appearance that starts from oneself, it is hoped that later it can provide an example or role model to prove to be an individual who can excel, especially in the educational sphere.

Students from broken-home families have a significant influence on the mentality of a student. This is what causes a student to have no interest in achieving. However, students from broken-home families can also damage a child's psyche so that in school, they act as they please, are not disciplined in class, they always make trouble and riot. This is done because they only want sympathy from their friends, even their teachers. To address this, the teacher or an educator must provide more attention and direction so that they are aware and able to excel. One of the institutions that aims to educate children other than the family is the school. This is because some parents leave their children's education to the school. A school is where children get an academic and moral education. Instilling moral values is one thing that is very important and must be given by a teacher to his students. Students' morality is fundamental because it will determine their future. Coaching various kinds of deviant behavior experienced by students needs to be carried out by an educator, in this case, the teacher. Teachers play a significant role and are responsible for achieving school learning goals. The teacher's task is not only a profession but also a humanitarian and social duty. When dealing with children who become broken homes, a good teacher should approach these students gently.

Speak from the heart when dealing with these children; be their friend, not their teacher, because they need a friend who can understand them and help them. The psychology of children from broken-home families is very sensitive, especially children who are victims of broken-home families (Sillekens & Notten, 2020). They tend to close themselves off and do not socialize, even as explained above, which can lead to negative behavior. Therefore, there is a need for a good approach from a teacher, namely by chatting with them outside of class hours. The role of the teacher in his professionalism dominates his success in student self-control. The teacher is a parent who naturally corrects a child's behavior so that he can continue to live his life as well as he should. The attention given by a teacher to his students, especially students with a terrible background coming from broken home families, is beneficial in straightening out the goals of this nation's education, namely to make young people intelligent and have noble character. For this reason, the role of the teacher is essential as a solution to overcoming the dilemmas of students who are victims of broken homes.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the research and analysis of the data that has been carried out while conducting the research, it can be concluded that the first is the psychology of social-emotional development of students who experience broken homes at senior high schools in Palu, namely from aspects of their social behavior, including like to talk or invite friends to talk, Likes to interact well with friends and teachers even though peers are less open in class, disciplined, polite with teachers or other people, has a sense of responsibility for doing assignments given by teachers and looks neat and obeys school rules, likes to help although sometimes they become quiet so that in terms of the social behavior of students who come from broken home families, in theory, it contradicts the

facts in the field. The second process analysis of the Islamic religious education learning approach that is effectively used for students who come from broken home families at senior high schools in Palu tends to use a different approach, applying six process approaches, namely stories or stories of successful people's struggles, in low-income families or children living by their parents.

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